

Effect of chemical seed treatments on productivity of upland rice

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Studies at the College of Agriculture, Calcutta University, showed that soaking stored seeds of various crops in water or solutions of certain chemicals for 2 to 3 h followed by drying greatly minimized the loss of vigor and viability during subsequent storage under natural conditions. We evaluated the hydration-dehydration seed treatment with and without chemicals and dry-dressing with calcium peroxide for improving yield of upland rice.

Five-month-old IR50 and CR237-1 seeds were soaked for 2.5 h in water or chemical solutions of different concentrations and then dried to their original weight. Seeds were dry-dressed in the calcium peroxide treatment. The experi-

Effect of seed treatment on rice growth and yield, Chinsurah, India, 1983.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²		Yield (t/ha)	
	CR237-1	IR50	CR237-1	IR50
Control	377	441	2.5	2.2
Water	405	472	2.7	2.5
Disodium phosphate (2 × 10 ⁻³ M)	426	510	3.0	2.7
Sodium chloride (5 × 10 ⁻³ M)	438	539	3.1	2.8
Potassium meta bisulfide (5 × 10 ⁻³ M)	419	490	2.9	2.5
Calcium peroxide (100 mg of CaO ₂ /g of seed)	414	464	2.9	2.5
Ethephon (10 ppm)	452	531	3.1	2.0
CD (0.05)	28		0.2 t/ha	

ment was under strict rainfed conditions in a randomized block design with three replications. Varieties were direct-seeded in lines at 20-cm between-row spacing.

The treatments significantly increased the number of panicles/m² and yield of both varieties (see table). The sodium

chloride treatment was best, followed by ethephon. Both treatments were significantly better than hydration alone. Simple hydration increased yield about 10% over the untreated control. The physicochemical basis of the beneficial effects is not yet understood. □

Efficiency of modified-urea materials applied at different N levels in lowland rice in the Cuu Long Delta

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In 1983 wet season, we evaluated the

Effect of modified-urea materials, applied at varying N rates, on grain yield and yield attributes of rice at Oman, Vietnam, 1983 wet season.

N level (kg/ha)	Form of urea material	Panicles/m ²	Spikelets/panicle	Unfilled spikelets (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0 (control)	None	256	62	17	26	3.1
	PU	293	68	17	27	3.6
	SCU	309	73	19	27	4.4
	USG	311	72	20	27	4.3
58	PU	304	71	20	27	3.9
	SCU	339	72	25	27	4.1
	USG	342	74	22	27	4.1
87	PU	349	73	22	27	4.3
	SCU	347	73	26	27	3.8
	USG	346	76	24	26	3.9
116	PU	357	70	27	28	3.9
	SCU	356	73	28	28	3.8
	USG	345	71	27	27	3.7
LSD (0.05)		41	9	7	NS	0.5

^aPU = prilled urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranules.

efficiency of prilled urea (PU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and urea supergranules (USG) at 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha in lowland transplanted rice in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. A no-N control was included to compute the efficiency of the treatments. The soil of the experimental plot was clayey with 0.18% total N, 0.04% total P, 0.77 meq Al³⁺/100 g soil, and

pH 4.6. Twenty-eight-d-old seedlings of early-maturing OM33 were transplanted on 1 Aug 1983 at 20 × 20-cm spacing using 2 seedlings/hill. All plots received 18 kg P/ha as superphosphate at transplanting. PU was broadcast in 2 splits: 2/3 at transplanting + 1/3 at panicle initiation. SCU was broadcast at transplanting, and USG was placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills in alternate rows 6 d after transplanting. The soil was flooded from transplanting to maturity. The crop was harvested on 27 Oct 1983.

At 29 kg N/ha, rice yields with SCU and USG were similar and significantly superior to those with PU (see table). At 58, 67, and 116 kg N/ha, PU, SCU, and USG did not differ significantly. Applying 29 kg N/ha as SCU or USG gave a yield response similar to that with 87 kg N/ha as PU. We observed a decreasing trend in grain yield with SCU and USG after 29 kg N/ha. With PU, yield increased to 87 kg N/ha and was significantly higher than that obtained with 29 kg N/ha. Plant height, spikelets/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight were not affected by N sources. Panicles/m² increased with increasing N supply. Reduced grain yield

with SCU and USG at higher N levels was caused by a higher percentage of unfilled spikelets.

The grain yield-predicting equations

for different urea materials were as follows:

$$\text{PU} : \hat{Y} = 3021 + 28.35 X - 0.1765 X^2$$

$$\text{SCU} : \hat{Y} = 3323 + 29.15 X - 0.2253 X^2$$

$$\text{USG} : \hat{Y} = 3281 + 28.99 X - 0.2253 X^2$$

where Y is expected grain yield (kg/ha) and X is kg N/ha. □

Effects of Zn application on direct-seeded rice in some alkaline soils in West Bengal

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As a part of the program to introduce modern rice varieties (MV) and optimum management practices to increase rice production in an integrated rural development project in West Bengal, we organized demonstration trials using different short-duration MVs in 1982 pre-kharif. The local farmers primarily grow a nondescript variety called IRRI that came from Bangladesh. It has short duration and fairly stable yields but is highly susceptible to many diseases and insect pests.

Nonreplicated demonstration trials were laid out in seven villages and compared IR36, IR50, and MW10 with the local IRRI.

Each variety was planted on 400 m² in each trial plot. Results from 16 trial plots grown by farmers of diverse socio-economic groups were averaged (see table). Because the local variety had Zn deficiency symptoms, Zn was applied in the trials.

Yield and ancillary characters of direct-seeded shortduration MVs and the effect of Zn application, West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	Plant ht (cm)		Effective tillers/hill		Spikelets (no./panicle)		Spikelet sterility (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)		Duration (d)	
	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T	C	T
IR36	85	90	18	22	75	132	18	18	3.6	4.6	2.8	3.2	103	105
IR50	90	90	28	28	183	185	55	20	3.0	4.0	2.5	2.8	105	105
MW10	100	107	24	25	154	162	40	10	4.1	4.8	5.2	5.2	103	105
IRRI	75	82	16	18	102	105	22	12	2.7	3.0	3.0	3.2	105	107

^a C = water-sprayed plot, T = Zn-sprayed plot.

Soils varied from heavy clay to loam, pH from 7.0 to 8.0, EC_e from 0.02 to 0.18 dS/m, organic carbon from 0.17 to 0.50%, available P from 18 to 70 kg/ha, and available K from 99 to 330. Five t farmyard manure/ha and 12-11-21 kg NPK/ha were applied basally. Aldrin 5% at 35 kg/ha was applied at land preparation. Seeds pretreated with 1 g carben-dazim/kg were dibbled, 5-6 seeds/hole, at 20- × 5-cm spacing and thinned to 3 seedlings/hole 15 d after emergence. Manual weeding was done at 20 and 40 d after sowing when 25 and 13 kg N/ha were applied. ZnSO₄ at 1% was sprayed on plants 30 and 45 d after sowing as a half-plot treatment. Water was sprayed

in the other half-plot. Plots were sown from 12 May to 2 Jun 1983. Yield data were recorded from the subplot and from 10 randomly selected plants from each subplot. Each subplot was considered a replication.

All three MVs yielded more grain than IRRI. MW10 yielded more straw than the other varieties. Applying Zn decreased spikelet sterility in IR50 and MW10, but not in IR36, perhaps because IR36 flowered unevenly. Zn application did increase the number of effective tillers and spikelets per panicle in IR36. Applying 16 kg ZnSO₄/ha in two 8-kg applications increased net profit on the rice crop by \$100/ha. □

Rice ratoon crop root systems

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Ratooning, the ability of the rice plant to regenerate tillers after harvest, is affected by many main crop environmental factors and cultural practices. Of several factors that determine ratooning potential, root vigor and distribution are probably very important.

We investigated the root distribution and changes in root dry weight of an IR44 ratoon crop at the IRRI farm in 1983 wet season. Mature plants were ratooned by cutting the stalks 15 cm

above the ground. Immediately after, 40 kg N/ha was topdressed. During main crop harvest wooden planks were used to minimize root damage. Ten plants were randomly selected at each sampling date, and plant and soil were removed to about 20-cm depth. Roots were washed and rated for distribution, then clipped and dried at 70°C to a constant weight. Roots from the mother culms and those from the ratoon tillers were separated 42 d after harvest (DH), at ratoon flowering (53 DH), and at ratoon harvest (75 DH).

At main crop harvest and up to 35 DH, 70-80% of the roots were reddish brown. A few plants had pale brown roots at main crop harvest. The propor-

tion of black (dead) roots increased with age. Some (1 to 5%) white (new) roots developed from nodes close to the ground. A fairly high (40 to 80%) amount of dead roots was observed from 35 to 75 DH. Beyond 42 DH, most plants had well-developed white roots from ratoon tillers, but some ratoon tillers lacked roots, indicating complete dependence on the main crop roots for nutrients.

Root dry weight differed significantly during ratoon development and growth. Root dry weight declined from 0 to 14 DH (see figure) because the nutrients for initial ratoon growth are supplied by the mother culms and roots. Part of the decrease may also be attributed to the